

SPECIFIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES

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***Annotation:** In the article, the concept of pedagogical technology, its factors of origin, necessity are discussed, and the necessity of its formation is also touched upon.*

***Key words:** pedagogue, pedagogical technologies, necessity, personnel, education, social attitude.*

The main essence of pedagogical technology is to engage students in education and achieve full mastery of knowledge. The main goal of the introduction of pedagogical technology is the thorough assimilation of the knowledge provided in education by the majority of students.

Scientific literature discusses three aspects of pedagogical technology: scientific, descriptive, and practical.

In the scientific aspect, the purpose, content and methods of teaching are scientifically based, and the pedagogical process is designed.

In the descriptive aspect, an algorithmic process is developed based on the participation of the purpose, content, methods and means of achieving the planned learning results.

Pedagogical technology process is implemented in practical aspect.

In relation to educational practice, three levels of pedagogical technology are defined: general pedagogical, special methodical, local (module).

Universal pedagogical technology represents a holistic educational process.

Special methodical technology consists of methods and means of implementing the educational process within one subject.

Local (modular) technology refers to the application of technology to special sections of the educational process. This technology is focused on solving special didactic and educational tasks.

The structure of pedagogical technology. It consists of a conceptual basis, the content of the educational process, and a technological process.

Each pedagogical technology is based on a certain scientific concept.

The scientific concept of pedagogical technology covers the philosophical, psychological, socio-pedagogical and didactic foundations of achieving educational goals.

The content of the educational process consists of the general and specific goals of the educational process, the content of the educational material.

The technological process covers the organization of the educational process, teacher activity, student activity, methods of educational process management, educational process diagnostics.

Researchers define criteria that satisfy any pedagogical technologies.

Consistency as a criterion of pedagogical technology includes the logicity of the process, the interdependence of all parts of the pedagogical technology, and its integrity.

One of the criteria of pedagogical technology is that it is based on management. It will consist of diagnosis of the educational process, planning and design of its implementation, changing it with teaching methods and tools.

The criterion of effectiveness of pedagogical technology envisages high results obtained in concrete conditions of the educational process.

Restoration is one of the criteria of pedagogical technologies. It includes the possibility of using pedagogical technologies in other educational institutions.

The technology has a universal nature, it can be implemented by every specialist, performed at the same level and achieve the intended goal. Its main difference from the methodology is that the methodology consists of a set of teaching methods and ways that are convenient for a certain person. The methodology depends on the teacher's knowledge, skills, abilities, personal qualities, and temperament. This can be seen by comparing the difference between programmed educational technology and intensive (intensive) teaching methods of various special subjects using different didactic tools.

Thus, the main criteria of technologies can be defined as follows:

- relying on a certain scientific basis, concept;
- systematicity, educational process and logical interdependence of its components;
- efficiency, guarantees the achievement of educational standards, that the required time, effort and means are at the standard level;
- reproducibility by others.

Pedagogical technology determines the system of organizing the influence of pedagogues on students and trainees to achieve professional and pedagogical goals.

Pedagogical technology provides an opportunity to organize pedagogical activity on the basis of specific goals and to control its technology.

Pedagogical technology system ensures clear implementation of pedagogical goals.

The main feature of a technological system is to guarantee the expected result. For this purpose, tasks to be performed at each stage of achieving the main goal, specific modules or algorithms of tools and methods required for this are created.

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